

WHITE PAPER

System Architecture

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**EUROPEAN TECHNOLOGY
PLATFORM FOR HIGH
PERFORMANCE COMPUTING**

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Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of the ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

This white paper examines the current state and future directions of High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems in the exascale era. It highlights key areas essential for maintaining and enhancing performance, efficiency, and sustainability.

Advanced cooling techniques, such as direct liquid and immersion cooling, are crucial for optimizing performance and reducing carbon emissions. Adaptive resource partitioning and energy-efficient designs are vital for handling the dynamic workloads typical of exascale systems. Robust monitoring tools for infrastructures and practices like heat reuse play significant roles in reducing operational costs and environmental impact.

System administration is enhanced by open-source tools and standards like RedFish, which improve administrative scalability, efficiency, and accessibility. Federated computing models should facilitate seamless exploitation of distributed resources, significantly boosting computational capabilities. Innovations in memory architectures address the growing demands for memory bandwidth and capacity, while disaggregated memory architectures and scalable pooling solutions enhance memory utilization and performance.

Advanced interconnect technologies, including photonic interconnects, are targeted to the critical latency and bandwidth requirements of next-generation data centres, and evolving network architectures are focused on improving data movement efficiency. Hybrid cloud models leverage both on-premises and cloud infrastructures, optimizing resource utilization and performance. Effective data management and integration strategies are crucial to overcoming challenges associated with latency, bandwidth, and interoperability.

Co-design approaches, integrating hardware and software development, are necessary to achieve reliability, fault tolerance, and energy efficiency. Emerging technologies, such as quantum computing and silicon photonics, offer new avenues for enhancing HPC and AI capabilities. Balancing security measures with usability is critical to maintaining productivity, and sustainable practices, including recycling and the use of renewable energy sources, are imperative for reducing the carbon footprint of HPC and AI systems.

At the system architecture level, the European Modular Supercomputing Architecture (MSA) is now established as a promising blueprint for efficient, truly heterogeneous systems. The challenges of ever-increasing system sizes, increasingly diverse and dynamic workloads, and importantly of establishing the compute continuum will require extension of that paradigm to fully support adaptive, dynamic orchestration and support of large-scale federated infrastructures.

In the following pages we outline the strategic directions and innovations required to drive the next wave of advancements in HPC and AI. By focusing on co-design, sustainable practices, and disruptive technologies, the full potential of exascale computing can be harnessed, ensuring that HPC and AI systems continue to support scientific, engineering, and societal advancements.

Glossary of Acronyms

- AI** – Artificial Intelligence
- CXL** – Compute Express Link
- DCIM** – Data Center Infrastructure Management
- DLC** - Direct Liquid Cooling
- DNA** - DeoxyriboNucleic Acid
- FPGA** – Field-Programmable Gate Array
- GPU** – Graphics Processing Unit
- HBM DRAM** – High Bandwidth Memory Dynamic Random Access Memory
- HDD** – Hard Disk Drive
- HPC** – High-Performance Computing
- IOPS** – Input/Output Operations Per Second
- IoT** – Internet of Things
- KPI** - Key Performance Indicator
- LDAP** – Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
- NVMe** – Non-Volatile Memory Express
- OSFP** – Octal Small Form Factor Pluggable
- PCIe** – Peripheral Component Interconnect Express
- RO** - Research Organization
- SLA** – Service Level Agreement
- SSD** – Solid State Drive
- TCO** – Total Cost of Ownership
- TDP** – Thermal Design Power
- TLA+** – Temporal Logic of Actions
- VPN** – Virtual Private Network

Introduction

The landscape of High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems is undergoing a significant transformation. This white paper describes the advancements and challenges in these cutting-edge domains, highlighting key areas such as system integration, energy efficiency, system administration, memory and storage hierarchies, network interconnects, and federated computing.

Achieving optimal performance and sustainability in exascale HPC and AI systems requires innovative cooling techniques, energy-efficient designs, and robust management frameworks. Advanced cooling methods, such as direct liquid and immersion cooling, are essential for reducing carbon emissions and operational costs, while adaptive resource partitioning addresses the dynamic workloads characteristic of these systems.

Open-source management tools and standards like RedFish enhance scalability and efficiency, making HPC and AI systems more accessible and manageable. Federated computing and hybrid cloud models facilitate seamless access to distributed resources, significantly boosting computational capabilities.

Innovations in memory architectures tackle the bandwidth and capacity demands of modern workloads. Additionally, advanced interconnect technologies, including photonic interconnects, address the critical latency and bandwidth needs of next-generation data centres.

This white paper offers a comprehensive overview of current technologies and future directions in HPC and AI, emphasizing the importance of co-design, disruptive technologies, and sustainable practices in driving the next wave of advancements in these fields.

State of the Art

System-level Heterogeneity, Packaging & Integration

With Moore's Law coming to an end, performance improvements cannot come anymore only from mere miniaturization of structures in processor manufacturing. Instead, higher compute performance requires specialization, with accelerators designed to perform specific kinds of operations in a very efficient manner. From the system architecture point of view this means that HPC systems must combine a variety of compute devices, making them available to users with diverse requirements. The most common approach is to build HPC systems with different partitions or modules, e.g. a CPU-only is put together with a GPU-accelerated module, so that users can allocate resources on both. This is the principle of the *Modular Supercomputing Architecture*¹, that has become by now standard practice.

HPC systems are designed at the data centre, rack, or motherboard level to optimize Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as performance, density, and energy efficiency. The community has been moving towards advanced cooling techniques like Direct Liquid Cooling (DLC) and even immersion cooling with heat reusage to reduce carbon emissions and cut costs. As discussed in the Hardware Components chapter, increasing the density of compute power per square meter is crucial in HPC design, necessitating efficient integration and cooling of high-power computing elements like CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs and AI accelerators.

Higher system density reduces the need for space in data centres and impacts HPC network architecture by shortening cable lengths, which reduces costs. Modern data centres employ various cable types, including passive and active copper, and optical cables, with decisions influenced by distance and cost. The evolving

technology in this area includes new cable types and connectors like high-density OSFP cables.

On the motherboard, the integration of CPUs or accelerators with high-speed interfaces (like PCIe/CXL, UALink and networks such as InfiniBand and Ethernet) support faster data processing and higher connectivity. Innovations in multi-die packages allow embedding components that were previously separate, altering the design considerations for items like HBM DRAM, which offers high bandwidth but poses new thermal and power dissipation challenges. This evolution calls for new design trade-offs and considerations in component integration.

Energy Efficiency and Sustainability

System architecture enhances energy efficiency by aligning system characteristics with application demands. This alignment ensures that all system components operate at optimal levels, preventing idle components from consuming unnecessary power. Given the diverse and dynamic workloads handled by typical High-Performance Computing (HPC) centres, data centres are applying tools (e.g. smart batch schedulers) and methods for implementing flexible and adaptive partitioning and distributing resources effectively, mapping each part of the workload to the part of the heterogeneous architecture that is best suited to deliver performance per watt per operation.

System architecture can enhance the efficiency of power supply and cooling subsystems. The adoption of single voltage supplies, the deployment of highly efficient power converters located near power-intensive components, and the implementation of advanced liquid cooling techniques are now

¹ E. Suarez et al., Modular Supercomputing Architecture, ETP4HPC White Paper, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6508394>

standard practices in modern high-performance computing systems.

A robust monitoring infrastructure that can analyse and correlate various performance metrics can improve energy efficiency through adaptive system management. In this context, Data Centre Infrastructure Management (DCIM) and HPC monitoring systems work in close collaboration to optimize the overall efficiency of data centres.

System Administration

HPC systems require specialized system administration software. Open-source HPC management tools like xCat and Warewulf provide cost-effective alternatives to proprietary software, making HPC more accessible to smaller research entities.

Key considerations include supporting a broad functionality range, managing users via LDAP, handling the deployment of diskless bare metal servers, and integrating accelerators into management and monitoring systems. These tools must support various interconnects like InfiniBand, Slingshot, and Ethernet.

The adoption of RedFish, an open hardware configuration and monitoring standard, is growing. Redfish allows in-band or out-of-band access and provides detailed information and functionality for efficient management. This integration enables dynamic control of hardware, optimizing for energy, cost efficiency, reliability, or availability. It supports scalability to tens of thousands of machines, which is necessary to support exascale systems.

The computing continuum facilitates novel big data use cases across the edge-cloud-supercomputer spectrum (e.g., federated HPC, sky computing, IoT). Fast data movement workflows rely on state-of-the-art architectures built on stream ingestion and file transfer open-source tools. Moreover, users struggle with diverse architectures: stream ingestion for small datasets and low latency, file transfer for large datasets and high throughput. Fast data movement should leverage a fast path in HPC supercomputers, enabling direct data transfer to compute modules, possibly including

memory pooling, bypassing slower storage paths. Technologies like GPUDirect facilitate this, though it's important to note that GPUDirect primarily addresses the path between HPC storage and GPUs, not external resources. This requires attention in both system administration and new architectures but is an innovation that will motivate academic and industry users to leverage HPC.

Memory and Storage Hierarchy

As high-performance computing (HPC) systems have entered in the exascale era, optimal resource allocation and utilization pose a continued challenge. Today, HPC architectures are equipped with memory, compute, and local storage (typically as a scratch area) tightly coupled within the node boundary. While such a static coarse-grained provisioning simplifies resource management, it does not support evolving HPC workloads, considering also that rapidly emerging AI workloads are imposing a significant stress on these traditional architectures. Because memory capacity and bandwidth are static resources and tightly coupled, over-provisioning (large memory capacity) is a potential but not effective solution to support the requirements of diverse large memory and bandwidth-intensive workloads, resulting in significant memory under-utilization when these workloads are not executed. Additionally, specialized accelerators like GPUs and FPGAs are becoming ubiquitous, and these heterogeneous compute units require adequately provisioned memory resources to sustain their performance. In particular, FPGAs allow relatively abundant local memory to be placed very close to computational resources, thus increasing energy efficiency by tailoring the lower levels of

the memory architecture to computational demands.

Therefore, HPC and AI workloads mandate configurable memory resources to achieve high performance and optimal resource utilization. Disaggregating memory from compute and providing on-demand and dynamic memory resources from memory pooling are poised to become an approach for improving memory utilization. Essentially, memory pooling mitigates single-node memory imbalance and provides temporary memory expansion to address memory requirements. Disaggregated solutions use network-attached memory as memory pools and provide software extensions to paging management to ease programming efforts. Scalable hardware-supported memory disaggregation and pooling is one objective of the Compute Express Link (CXL) standard. CXL is an open standard for interconnecting processors, accelerators, and memory. Hardware conforming to the CXL standard provides low-latency, high-bandwidth data access transparently to application codes. While the features of CXL may bring significant benefits, the adoption of CXL-based infrastructure in HPC is in the early stages mostly because of the limited number of CPU supporting such a standard.

HPC and AI systems employ a sophisticated storage hierarchy to optimize performance and capacity, balancing speed, capacity, and cost. This hierarchy typically includes NVMe SSDs and HDDs as well as tape libraries for long term storage. SSDs are deployed at the top tier due to their superior performance, providing fast data access and low latency. They are ideal for applications requiring high IOPS, such as AI model training and real-time data analytics. Current PCIe Gen5 NVMe SSDs can sustain I/O bandwidths exceeding 10 GB/s and over 2 million IOPS. This capability allows parallel storage architectures to achieve aggregate bandwidths of multiple terabytes per second by integrating numerous storage servers equipped with NVMe SSDs and connected via high-speed fabrics such as InfiniBand. Below the SSD tier, HDDs offer a cost-effective solution for high-capacity storage, suitable for storing large volumes of infrequently accessed data.

This helps manage overall storage costs while providing ample capacity. Data management software dynamically moves data between tiers based on access patterns and performance needs, ensuring efficient storage utilization. Tape storage is used as cold storage, and is regaining popularity due to its large capacity and low energy costs. This is addressed in the Emerging Architectures chapter, so is not discussed in depth here.

Network and Interconnect

The rapid expansion of computing elements in supercomputing systems introduces new challenges, particularly in the area of interconnect technologies. High-performance interconnects like Nvidia InfiniBand and NVLink, Cornelis Omni-Path, HPE Slingshot, or Eviden BXI are integral to modern supercomputers. While these technologies continue to advance in performance, their development pace lags behind that of overall computing capacity. Moreover, the lack of compatibility among these interconnect technologies necessitates the use of costly gateways that diminish speed and increase latency. To address this issue, the UltraEthernet Consortium is developing a comprehensive architecture designed to optimize Ethernet for high-performance AI and HPC networking called Ultra Ethernet. The consortium also works on an alternative to NVLink called UALink.

Communication latency, important when scaling up to millions of processors and managing exabytes of data, must be on the order of nanoseconds. Other critical considerations are power consumption, quality

of service assurance for highly heterogeneous workloads, congestion control and prevention and a highly effective dynamic routing algorithm to ensure a high resiliency of the network.

Looking ahead, next-generation data centres and HPC systems must focus on technologies that enhance data movement efficiency. Photonic die-to-die interconnections are a promising technology. Signals transmitted optically benefit from high bandwidth, and low power consumption. The conversion from electrical to optical (and back again) has a cost, so to be effective as a technology the savings and performance must outweigh the costs of conversion. Emphasizing technologies that optimize latency and bandwidth at all communication levels, from individual chips to data centre-wide networks, is fundamental for enhancing peak performance in future supercomputing initiatives.

System Level Modelling and Simulation

End users in industry and academia focus on assessing and modelling HPC systems to maximize utilization and performance, including energy efficiency and reliability. This involves benchmarking, simulations, and modelling through analytical methods and simulations. As HPC systems grow in complexity, predicting their behaviour becomes increasingly challenging. Current simulation environments lack the capability to provide detailed insights for systems with thousands of computing elements, requiring research into new methods using accelerators and ML/AI techniques for Exascale systems.

Over 20% of computing capacity in high-performance systems is lost to failures and recovery actions², highlighting the need for fault tolerance to reduce total cost of ownership (TCO). HPC algorithms and systems must be designed to exploit parallelism, minimize communication overhead, and

efficiently use resources like multicore processors and accelerators. Errors can lead to significant consequences, from inaccurate scientific results to security breaches. Algorithm design and formal verification, such as using TLA+ (Temporal Logic of Actions)³, enhance reliability and correctness in HPC applications.

Despite its importance, system design and verification are often overlooked. The advent of Exascale computing complicates system and algorithm development, increasing the potential for bugs due to inadequate design. Solid system design is of key importance for building, running, maintaining, and evolving distributed systems and concurrent algorithms, especially at Exascale levels. Additionally, leading companies like Oracle, Microsoft, and Amazon emphasize reverse engineering of formal specifications to ensure system correctness and to find and correct bugs.

Given the fundamental importance of HPC for science discoveries and engineering simulations, incorporating system design and verification into educational curricula would benefit the HPC community.

Federated Computing in Heterogeneous HPC

Traditionally, users access scientific HPC systems by individually applying for accounts and selecting specific systems for their applications, using centre-specific credentials. Federated computing is a growing technology that may change this by allowing users to access systems across multiple centres from a pooled array of federated systems, ideally enabling applications to automatically run on the most available system under service-level agreements. For example, a “fastest result” SLA might direct an application to the fastest system in the pool according to the availability of resources.

Federated computing requires HPC centres to adopt a common identity authentication

² Snir et al, Addressing failures in exascale computing, <https://snir.cs.illinois.edu/listed/J57.pdf>

³ <https://lamport.azurewebsites.net/tla/tla.html>

scheme, manage quotas and possibly pay-per-use through these federated identities, and offer higher-level discovery, reservation, and meta-scheduling services. It requires automated processes for rerouting application execution between centres and ensuring necessary data accessibility. This approach extends support beyond computing resources to include data, network, and large instruments.

Cloud and Data Infrastructures

Currently and albeit at different degrees of distribution, hybrid cloud models are being adopted where HPC workloads are distributed between on-premises infrastructure and cloud platforms. Large Hyperscalers are usually the ‘overflow’ resources used for such a distribution. This approach leverages the cloud for burst capacity, storage, and specific computational tasks that can benefit from cloud-native features. Despite these advancements, significant challenges persist. The primary challenge is the high latency and bandwidth limitations associated with transferring large datasets between HPC and cloud systems. Ensuring data integrity and security during transit is also critical, particularly for sensitive or proprietary information. Furthermore, the cost of data egress from cloud platforms can be prohibitive, impacting the overall cost-effectiveness of hybrid solutions. Interoperability between different systems and software environments adds another layer of complexity, requiring robust data management and integration strategies. Addressing these challenges is essential for optimizing performance and efficiency in hybrid HPC-cloud architectures.

Architecture in the Digital Continuum

Today, there is a growing number of devices connecting to the Internet, generating, collecting, computing and sharing data. This is giving rise to new needs that are not covered by traditional paradigms, where computation needs to be distributed among several devices with very different capabilities and calculations performed where it is most efficient. Within this context, the Digital Continuum paradigm emerges as more than a simple combination of HPC, Cloud, Edge, and IoT functionalities; it represents a fluid cyberinfrastructure creating a fully integrated wildly heterogeneous system-of-systems capable of operating across all layers in a decentralized, secure, and efficient manner. In this way, the system heterogeneity that exists on premises (e.g. in the form of modular supercomputers, see section “System-level heterogeneity, packaging and integration”), is extended across a federated infrastructure of computing devices with diverse hardware configurations and in diverse locations. Deployment of an effective and usable Digital Continuum relies on the EU-wide high-performance network and a number of federated platforms. This infrastructure is the initial step for a more wide-ranging and integrated system-of-systems architecture, designed to address the trade-offs between needs, functionalities and capabilities in the chain of components it is built on. It must also take into account the wide-ranging sources of data, as well as establish the rules (e.g. API) for interconnecting the devices, all while being flexible enough to enable the implementation of new functionalities and/or new devices.

HPC for Urgent Decision Making

Technological advances are creating new opportunities to expand HPC beyond traditional engineering and scientific computational workloads. A significant opportunity is applying HPC to respond to time-sensitive societal issues and environmental disasters, such as disease outbreaks, wildfires, hurricanes, extreme flooding, earthquakes, tsunamis, severe winter weather, and industrial accidents. The use of HPC for COVID-19 pandemic simulations exemplifies its value in urgent decision-making⁴.

Addressing incident response necessitates a federated, coordinated, and distributed infrastructure that combines data ingestion from multiple sources, computing, numerical models (Digital Twins), and specialized decision support systems to generate actionable information. Conventional HPC usage modes, which rely on long-term, time-scheduled resource allocation and policies that maximize resource usage across many users, are inadequate for these urgent scenarios. Incident response teams must access and utilize resources in real-time based on evolving situations, requiring the ability to allocate resources on-demand with minimal or no advance notice. This includes the need for pre-empting already running applications or workflows, dynamic resource allocation and scheduling, and multi-centre coordination for resource managers. With pre-emption and dynamic allocation, users would greatly benefit from state preservation to avoid losing pre-empted work. Furthermore, the interactive steering of simulations, i.e. tools enabling the on-demand and interactive modification of parameters of the run such as the number of nodes, the allocation of the run on the nodes, the transfer of the run to other centres, is necessary for adapting to the immediate needs of disaster response efforts.

⁴ “Lessons learned from urgent computing in Europe: Tackling the COVID-19 pandemic”,

<https://www.pnas.org/doi/epdf/10.1073/pnas.2024891118>

Upcoming Challenges (2025 – 2028)

Efficient and Resilient Orchestration, Management and Use of Heterogeneous Resources

One promise of the compute/digital continuum is to offer applications a flexible and transparent view of the resources available across a large, multi-level Internet-connected infrastructure. Realizing the full benefits of such a continuum requires overcoming several complex challenges. These challenges include accessing geographically distributed platforms, matching services and resources, harnessing resource heterogeneity, and adapting service deployments to dynamic changes in resources and applications. A number of developments, such as wider interconnectivity across data centres and edge compute devices, hardware heterogeneity at all levels, the federation of data centres and the requirements of urgent computing, make addressing these challenges ever more urgent. At a higher level, the Modular Supercomputing Architecture (MSA) developed in EU funded DEEP & SEA Projects and used in JUPITER, Europe's first Exascale system, is a notable example of an infrastructure paradigm addressing these challenges.

Orchestration, management, and efficient use of heterogeneous resources in large, potentially geographically dispersed networks is challenging and must address the dynamic requirements of various types of workloads according to predefined strategies. This approach eliminates the need for multiple, potentially incompatible specialized tools by offering a unified platform that supports a variety of technologies. Consequently, it boosts productivity by allowing developers and users to select the most suitable system or system component for each task, fostering collaboration, standardization, and data sharing across different organizations. The need for truly dynamic and adaptive orchestration and management for such a scenario cannot be overstated. Today, the MSA is focused on efficiently handling

heterogeneous resources in a single HPC/AI centre – its extension to cover several centres and significant parts of the compute continuum and become fully dynamic seems a promising way to address the challenges mentioned in the first paragraph above.

Containers, as a lightweight application virtualization technology, have gained popularity and serve as the ideal complement to orchestration platforms for deploying diverse workloads. They support agile application deployment, environmental consistency, OS portability, application-centric management, and resource isolation.

Several technology vendors are addressing challenges like inter-system compatibility, security, and allocation of resources, and are also proposing standards with the hope of getting them universally adopted. Above and beyond that, creating an effective orchestration platform suitable for the complexities of networked heterogeneous systems poses additional key requirements, which may be eased by promoting and adopting an open standard. These include support for seamless reallocation of jobs without losing the task's progress, configuration of heterogeneous jobs on heterogeneous platforms, optimization of initial container placement into existing resources through tools like task packing, and cluster size adjustment through auto-scaling algorithms to meet changing workloads. Additionally, an effective rescheduling mechanism should be included to enable

shutting down underutilized partitions for cost and energy savings.

Effective orchestration platforms must incorporate real-time monitoring to be able to place workloads and workflow steps on the right set of resources and meet QoS and energy efficiency targets. They also need to include advanced fault-tolerance mechanisms, automated recovery processes to promptly detect and address any issues affecting system operation and reliability. By embedding resiliency into the framework, the whole infrastructure and its participating organizations can achieve higher reliability and performance, minimizing downtime and ensuring seamless user experiences even in the face of disruptions.

Integration of Disruptive Technologies

The race for technological supremacy is accelerating across multiple domains, with today's innovators positioned to dominate the future. To win this race, Europe must develop a common and effective approach to integrate emerging and disruptive technologies at the HW/SW/system levels with scientific and engineering workflows, with the objective of providing benefits to the scientific and industrial end-users, the operators of the compute and data infrastructures and society as a whole (through a reduction of the CO₂ footprint, for instance). This strategy should encompass careful preliminary evaluations of disruptive technologies to select optimal deployment approaches within the broader context of the digital transformation, including evolutionary, adaptive, and revolutionary methods.

Several qualitative and quantitative factors must be considered when evaluating disruptive technologies. These include:

- **Need:** What specific requirements, addressed by the disruptive technology, are currently unmet or inadequately served?
- **Time:** The time required to effectively integrate and deploy a disruptive technology into an existing workflow.

- **Impact:** The potential influence of disruptive technologies.
- **Cost:** The level of effort required to deploy, sustain and support the disruptive technology.
- **Risk:** The uncertainties of a new and unproven technology, and the possible mitigation/workaround actions.
- **Policy Challenges:** The extent of non-technological barriers associated with implementing the disruptive technology into current workflows.

By addressing these factors, the European HPC and AI ecosystem (ROs, public and private entities) can ensure the successful integration of disruptive technologies, driving innovation and maintaining a competitive edge in the global technological landscape. Disruptive technologies that warrant consideration include DNA computing, specific accelerators, silicon photonics, and quantum computing.

Modelling and Predicting Performance, Power Consumption and Behaviour of Highly Heterogeneous and Complex Systems

Modelling and predicting the performance, power consumption, energy efficiency, and behaviour of heterogeneous and complex HPC and AI systems pose significant challenges. These systems usually integrate a variety of components, including CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, and custom accelerators, each with distinct performance and power characteristics. Accurately modelling these diverse elements requires sophisticated tools and methodologies capable of capturing the interactions and dependencies among them.

It is challenging to comprehensively model performance and power consumption under different workloads and operating conditions. Models must account for the dynamic nature of modern computing environments, where workloads can vary significantly over time. Additionally, the integration of AI workloads, which are often unpredictable and resource-intensive, complicates the modelling process.

Another challenge is the validation and calibration of models. The extensive benchmarking and fine-tuning required for calibration can be time-consuming and resource-intensive. The complexity of the systems further exacerbates this issue, as even minor inaccuracies in the model can lead to significant discrepancies in predictions.

Predicting system behaviour also involves understanding the impact of software optimizations and system configurations. This requires detailed knowledge of both hardware architecture and software stack, including compilers, libraries, and runtime environments. The more heterogeneous the system, the more intricate the interplay between the components, making it more difficult to produce accurate predictions.

Lastly, there is the challenge of scalability. As HPC and AI systems scale up to include thousands of nodes and millions of cores, modelling and predicting their behaviour becomes exponentially more complex. Scalable modelling techniques and efficient algorithms are essential to handle the sheer size and complexity of these systems. The use of advanced AI methods complementing traditional approaches bears promise here.

Addressing these challenges will require advances in modelling techniques, enhanced tools for measuring performance and power, and a deeper understanding of the interactions between heterogeneous components. Collaboration between hardware designers, software developers, AI experts and system architects will be important for the development of next-generation, accurate and reliable models that can guide the design and optimization of future HPC and AI systems. The application of AI methods and models may have a significant impact on the in-depth understanding of the interactions, taking into

account the complex interdependencies among the components.

Energy Efficiency and Monitoring

The arrival of next-generation CPUs and accelerators will increase energy density, even as they boost energy efficiency. In the last few years, the TDP of CPUs and GPUs has skyrocketed, bringing an increase of performance but requiring advanced cooling techniques. The trend is for a further increase of the TDP, fuelled by the insatiable requirements of AI workflows.

Two-phase direct cooling is emerging as a favourable solution due to its enhanced cooling capacity and energy efficiency. This method leverages the latent heat of vaporization, dissipating significant amounts of heat with minimal energy input for pumps. Mudawar⁵ highlights that two-phase cooling systems can manage heat loads exceeding 1 kW/cm², making them suitable for high-density HPC environments. Robert Curtis et al⁶ analyse five different cooling technologies currently available for the data centres, comparing cooling performance, cost, and reliance on facility chilled water supplies. A more recent implementation of a two-phase immersion cooling solution has been developed by GIGABYTE with LiquidStack and 3M, achieving a PUE 1.01.

Moreover, two-phase cooling systems offer higher temperature outputs than DLC, which can be reused for other applications such as district heating, thus improving overall energy efficiency.

Despite their advantages, two-phase direct cooling systems typically require engineered liquids such as fluorocarbons. These coolants, while effective, pose environmental challenges. They are more harmful than water and

⁵ Mudawar, I. (2011). Assessment of High-Heat-Flux Thermal Management Schemes. *IEEE Transactions on Components and Packaging Technologies*, 24(2), 122-141.

⁶ Curtis, G. et al (2023). Performance Comparison of Five Data Center Server Thermal Management

Technologies. 2023 39th Semiconductor Thermal Measurement, Modeling & Management Symposium (SEMI-THERM), DOI: 10.23919/SEMI-THERM59981.2023.10267908

generally require careful handling and disposal to mitigate environmental impact.

Farther down the road, die-level cooling techniques, many of them relying on microfluids circulating in channels within dies or 3D die stacks could offer additional heat transfer capability; these must be accommodated at the device design and packaging stage, which poses adoption challenges. An in-depth analysis of the microfluidic technology is reported in “Microfluidics: Cooling inside the chip” (<https://www.datacenterdynamics.com/en/analysis/microfluidics-cooling-inside-the-chip/>).

Increasing TDPs also pose significant challenges for power supplies. Enhanced power supply efficiency will be critical, requiring innovations such as single voltage supplies and highly efficient power converters positioned near power-intensive components, not to mention the requirement to cool these devices.

The heterogeneous nature of HPC and AI workloads requires sophisticated resource partitioning and distribution methods. Each workload component should be mapped to the architecture component that provides lowest energy use while satisfying performance requirements. This entails the development of more adaptive and flexible methods for resource allocation to accommodate the diverse and dynamic demands of modern HPC environments.

A major challenge is the establishment of a robust and comprehensive monitoring infrastructure, which must be capable of analysing and correlating performance metrics across all system components and heterogeneous technologies to facilitate adaptive system management.

As technologies such as DNA computing, domain specific accelerators, silicon photonics, and quantum computing emerge, their integration into existing HPC and AI systems will introduce additional complexity in energy monitoring and efficiency. Each of these technologies will have unique power and cooling requirements, necessitating tailored solutions to manage their energy consumption effectively.

Co-Design

The emergence of demanding AI applications, the proliferation of choices for hardware components, the complexity and scale of architecting and implementing the optimal solutions for future HPC systems mandate co-design based on a pragmatic methodology. As systems scale to the thousands or even hundreds of thousands of nodes, hardware/software co-design methodology is critical for achieving reliability and fault tolerance while maximizing energy efficiency without impacting performance and overall system effectiveness.

The main challenges posed by large node count systems on the hardware/software co-design approach are:

- Mitigate Technical Risk: Co-design allows for the identification and mitigation of technical risks early in the development process.
- Optimize Design Constraints: Co-design optimizes various design constraints leading to more efficient and economical solutions.
- Design for the failure rate of components: Failures (HW and SW) will happen and failure propagation (both at the application level as well at the HW level) should be prevented.
- Include evolving technologies/innovations: With expertise across a variety of technologies, a co-design team can leverage the complexities of different technologies and eliminate the need to build specialized expertise in-house.

However, as complexity at the component level grows and the system level scales, extra care must be applied to the hardware/software co-design methodology to avoid overfitting and/or creating fragile designs which can lead to performance cliffs outside of the optimal design points. CD/CI (continuous development/continuous integration) allows evaluation of the HW/SW technology behaviour at different scales (from node level to full system level) for reduction of design fragility. Moreover, a solid hardware/software co-design approach and simulation framework

can accelerate design exploration and Pareto-optimisation of future HPC system designs, facilitating the evaluation of constraints such as energy efficiency, environmental impacts, application performance, Total cost of Ownership (TCO) and system-wide reliability. In fact, the technological challenge for designing future systems resides in the ability of developing accurate Digital Twin of components and systems (considered as a collection of components) as 'standard design tools' for use in simulation, prediction, and control of physical systems.

Security

A primary challenge in securing HPC systems is maintaining usability while implementing stringent security measures. Researchers and scientists require seamless access to HPC resources to conduct their work efficiently. There is a tension between ease of use and security, as overly restrictive security protocols can hinder productivity by impeding legitimate access and workflows. Balancing usability with necessary security measures requires careful design and policy formulation.

Effective security in HPC systems demands significant administrative effort and dedicated resources to support regular updates, patch management, user access control, and incident response planning. Ensuring that administrative tasks do not overwhelm IT staff or detract from other critical activities is a significant challenge. Automation tools and streamlined processes can help mitigate this overhead but require investment, attention and training.

HPC systems often require connectivity to other sites for collaborative research, data sharing, and distributed computing. This connectivity introduces additional security risks, such as unauthorized access, data breaches, and network vulnerabilities. Ensuring secure communication channels and protecting data in transit, while maintaining the necessary level of connectivity, is complex and resource-intensive. Secure VPNs, encryption, and multi-factor authentication are necessary but must

be balanced against performance impacts and user convenience.

Security challenges become even more pronounced when dealing with highly sensitive data, such as health related data of citizens. Privacy regulations, such as GDPR in Europe, mandate rigorous data protection and privacy measures. The risk of data breaches involving private information can have severe consequences, including legal penalties, loss of public trust, and significant harm to individuals' privacy. Ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive and private data necessitates advanced encryption techniques, robust access controls, and continuous monitoring to detect and respond to potential threats. Additionally, creating secure environments for data analysis and sharing that comply with regulatory requirements adds another layer of complexity and cost.

Sustainability and Recycling

The energy consumption of HPC systems is a growing factor and contributes to a significant carbon footprint. Transitioning to renewable energy sources, optimizing energy usage and reusing heat are essential. Current state-of-the-art cooling technologies in HPC systems include direct liquid cooling and immersion cooling. These methods are more efficient than traditional air cooling, providing better thermal management and reducing energy consumption.

More engineering resources must be allocated to the development of energy-efficient hardware and algorithms to lower operational costs and minimize environmental impact. Hardware includes components such as FPGAs and accelerators, which are less flexible and harder to program than CPUs but vastly more

energy efficient. Mapping a heterogeneous application to a heterogeneous platform and memory architecture while optimizing performance and energy efficiently is challenging.

Recycling HPC and AI systems must account for the complexity and diversity of materials used in their construction. These systems are composed of various rare earth metals, hazardous substances, and intricate components that are difficult to disassemble and thus costly to recycle effectively. Traditional recycling processes are often inadequate, leading to the accumulation of e-waste. Enhancing recycling methods to handle these sophisticated devices will require innovation in material science and recycling technologies. Policymakers and industry leaders must collaborate to establish standards and incentives that promote sustainable practices.

Post Exascale Vision

Many of the challenges described in the former sections are not new, but are exacerbated as systems grow to Exascale and beyond. The larger the system, the more critical energy consumption and fault tolerance become, which should trigger a fundamental rethinking of the role and targets of HPC.

The computer market and technology landscape are changing. Cloud services already deliver Exaflops of compute power for private customers and researchers. The classical division between high performance computing (running large-scale, tightly coupled applications) and high throughput computing (many small applications executed independently) in data centres and the cloud is becoming less clear. Cloud service providers are deploying very large-scale computing centres that provide compute capacity with high-speed networks and HPC software layers. Applications in Artificial Intelligence (AI), such as Large Language Models, are driving this trend. The choice between compute time on a HPC centre or with a Cloud Service Provider (CSP) frequently boils down to the cost of compute time on the cloud vs. the delay in availability of compute time in an HPC centre. Reducing the entry barrier for HPC, both in terms of time and required expertise, should be examined.

The technology landscape is strongly influenced by the economic drive of AI. The processor industry has a much stronger financial motivation to optimize a product for AI than for HPC. A clear consequence is the increasing silicon area dedicated to reduced-precision arithmetic, relative to double precision used in HPC. Application developers in HPC should rethink their approaches and reduce precision if possible, since this will automatically increase compute performance and energy efficiency. Of note is the development of processors by hyperscalers for their internal infrastructure and for cloud services. These processors are not offered as products, creating a class of processors that cannot be integrated in HPC centres. This has had a positive net benefit for the HPC

community to date, as it has driven both processor design and ecosystem development forward. But the concern is that it will impact the future of merchant processor development, forcing a choice between adapt to cloud solutions in order to benefit from hyperscalers' technology advances, or develop 'boutique' solutions tailored to HPC.

The slowing of Moore's law motivates new ideas leading to new products. Licensing as well as open standard approaches (e.g. RISC-V) are facilitating innovation. In the recent year a number of neuromorphic accelerators for AI (SpiNNaker, Graphcore, etc.), but also general-purpose processors (Fujitsu A64Fx, SiPearl Rhea, etc.) have been developed. They bring hope for further increases in performance and energy efficiency through tailored designs and specialization. Totally new approaches such as quantum computing are also being evaluated. These new processing choices make it more important than ever to design HPC systems in a flexible manner that enables the integration of diverse technologies, each tailored to a set of applications in the user portfolio. This, in turn, makes mandatory software developments for an efficient share and use of resources, as well as towards performance portability.

Key R&I Recommendations

Dynamic Resource Management and Disaggregated Resources (Mid TRL)

Dynamic resource management and disaggregated resources are increasingly available for optimizing HPC and AI systems' performance and efficiency. Increasing system heterogeneity and the dynamic nature of workloads necessitate adaptive methods for resource allocation. Research in this area is vital to developing flexible, energy-efficient systems capable of meeting the diverse and evolving demands of exascale computing environments.

Dynamic Resource Management and Disaggregated Resources within a Federated Computing Framework (Low TRL)

Federated computing with common identity authentication can reduce entry barriers by providing a unified interface to HPC and AI resources. When combined with dynamic resource management and disaggregated resources, this framework enables efficient energy and hardware allocation, making it possible the use of renewable energy. It can support advanced fault-tolerance mechanisms, including automated recovery processes and resource reallocation, as well as rerouting applications between centres. Additionally, it facilitates real-time resource allocation and dynamic management, crucial for urgent decision-making. This integrated approach enhances the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of next-generation HPC and AI systems.

Energy and Resource Efficiency (High TRL)

Research should focus on optimizing resource usage and developing highly efficient algorithms to ensure components operate effectively. Advanced cooling technologies,

particularly two-phase direct cooling, will be needed to manage high heat loads and reduce energy consumption. Implementing systems to capture and reuse heat for applications like district heating will enhance overall energy efficiency. Advanced power management techniques can dynamically adjust power usage based on workload demands and energy prices. Enhancing federated computing models to relocate jobs to data centres with better energy efficiency will optimize costs and make it possible the use of renewable energy. Additionally, the balance between improving resource utilization through disaggregated resources and scalable pooling solutions vs the increased complexity of the solution should be carefully assessed with respect to the objective of further increase energy efficiency while reducing hardware requirements. Addressing these areas will significantly enhance the energy and resource efficiency of next-generation HPC and AI systems.

Conclusions

The future of HPC and AI systems in the exascale era depends on key innovations and strategic approaches. Advanced cooling techniques promise to improve heat management and reduce carbon emissions. Adaptive resource partitioning coupled with federation techniques and energy-efficient designs accommodate dynamic workloads, maintaining performance and sustainability.

Open-source tools and standards enhance system administration by improving scalability, efficiency, and accessibility. Federated computing models boost computational capabilities by providing seamless access to distributed resources. Innovations in memory architectures and advanced interconnect technologies, including photonic interconnects, meet the demands for higher memory bandwidth and network efficiency.

Hybrid cloud models can reduce initial hardware investment and can be utilized in peak scenarios, but they require effective data management strategies to address latency, bandwidth, and interoperability challenges. Co-design approaches, integrating hardware and software development, ensure reliability, fault tolerance, and energy efficiency. Emerging technologies, such as quantum computing and silicon photonics, offer promising enhancements to HPC and AI capabilities.

Balancing security with usability is crucial for productivity, while sustainable practices, including renewable energy sources and recycling, reduce the carbon footprint of HPC and AI systems. By focusing on co-design, sustainable practices, and disruptive technologies, we can drive advancements in HPC and AI, supporting scientific, engineering, and societal progress.

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